

**PREDICTING THE STALL ONSET OF AN AXIAL-FLOW COMPRESSOR WITH RADIAL
INLET DISTORTION BASED ON GLOBAL LINEAR STABILITY ANALYSIS**

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Abstract

This paper presents an investigation of the effects of radial inlet distortion on compressor flow stability based on global linear stability analysis. The steady flow fields of a transonic compressor operating with clean inlet condition and radial inlet distortions were simulated, which are the objects of stability analysis. Two reduced-order stall inception models, streamline model and meridional surface model, were used to analyse the stability of these flow fields and predict the stability boundaries. The calculating results of streamline model indicated that the tip region is the most unstable part and the stability of the flow field in the tip region gradually worsens with the increase of the intensity of the radial inlet distortion. Meridional surface model further confirmed the unfavorable influence of radial inlet distortion on the flow stability and gave a quantitative assessment of the stall margin loss due to radial inlet distortion. The stability analysis results showed that the compressor flow stability has a strong correlation with the blade loading level of the tip region. The forward sweep feature was adopted to offset the harmful effects of the increase of the blade loading at the tip region induced by the radial inlet distortion, the validity of which was confirmed by both streamline model and meridional model.

I. Introduction

For an aero-engine installed in a military aircraft, the inlet flow cannot be so ideal that the compressor can operate without any loss of the nominal stall margin, due to the existence of inlet flow distortion caused by the flow separation in the intake, the growth of the boundary layer, the ingestion of large-scale turbulence or some other

possible unfavourable factors [1, 2]. Because of the unbearable consequences of the flow instabilities, such as rotating stall and surge, it is of great significance to assess the effects of inlet distortion on the compressor flow stability. During the past decades, a large amount of experimental and theoretical work has been done on this topic [2-5].

The inlet distortions induced by different causes can be quite different from each other. According to the steadiness of the inlet flow, the inlet distortions can roughly be divided into steady and unsteady types [6]. In fact, there is no absolutely steady inlet distortion. If the characteristic time scale of the inlet flow is long enough from a compressor point of view, then the inlet distortion can be regarded as steady. Conversely, the unsteadiness of the inlet distortion must be carefully taken into consideration when the time scale of the inlet flow is comparable with the rotating period of the compressor. In multi-spool engines, rotating stall in the upstream compressor will impose a non-uniform and rotating inlet condition on the downstream compressor, which is a typical unsteady type of distortion [2, 7]. Except for some special cases, most types of inlet distortion can be viewed as steady ones, considering the fact that the compressor usually rotates quite fast, while the aircraft manoeuvring happens over several seconds or even longer.

Among many different forms of inlet flow distortions, total pressure distortions are the most commonly encountered. Although the total pressure distortions generally have both radial and circumferential variations, it is very useful and convenient to break them at least conceptually, into radial and circumferential non-uniformities and investigate them separately. In 1960s, Reid [1] conducted a series of experiments to investigate the effects of inlet distortions on the overall performance and flow stability of a compressor by systematically varying the inlet total pressure patterns and levels. The experimental results show that the effects of radial

distortions on the stall margin of a compressor are much less severe than the circumferential ones. For this reason, much more attention has been paid to the latter than the former. However, it does not mean that it is nonsignificant or meaningless to investigate the radial distortions. After all, substantial radial non-uniformities still exist within a compressor with clean inlet conditions. Essentially radial inlet distortions will affect the radial equilibrium and redistribute the flow fields radially, and therefore result in a new spanwise distribution of the blade loading. In this sense, to investigate the radial distortions is helpful for us to get a better understanding of the mechanism that how the radial non-uniformities affect the overall performance and the flow stability and guide the compressor design.

In the early phase, most researchers focused on the flow stability prediction of compressors operating with uniform inlet flow and proposed various forms of stall inception model based on small perturbation theory, which indeed provide valuable insight into the flow instabilities in compressors [8-11]. Hynes and Greitzer [3] firstly developed an analytical model to predict the stall inception of a compressor with circumferential inlet distortion, which can be regarded as an extension of the classical Moore-Greitzer model [8]. The major modification of the model for the case with distortion is that, the flow coefficient is no longer a constant but is a strong function of the tangential coordinate, and therefore the derivative of the pressure rise coefficient with respect to the flow coefficient also varies with the tangential coordinate. It is the circumferential non-uniformities that introduce nonlinearities that couple each circumferential mode. However, for the cases with circumferentially uniform inlet condition, such as uniform or radial distortion inlet condition, the harmonics are still decoupled. It should be emphasized that both the Moore-Greitzer model and the modified one were established under the assumption of high hub-to-tip ratio and thus are essentially two-dimensional models, in addition, the axial variation of the basic flow was ignored. Although these two simplified analytical models have reproduced some experimental trends and revealed the effects on flow stability of different compressor parameters, the simplifications of the basic flow would limit their further applications. Obviously, the cases with radial non-uniformities or radial distortion can hardly be considered in these models. In order to investigate the effects of inlet distortions on the compressor flow stabilities, the non-uniformities of the flow fields need to be well included, otherwise there is no interaction between the non-uniformities of the basic flow and the possible small disturbances. Thanks to the progress made in computer science and computational fluid dynamics, it is relatively easy to obtain the steady flow fields with inlet distortion through steady viscous numerical simulations.

In addition to carefully deal with the non-uniformities of the basic flow, the blade row modelling is also critical for the stall inception prediction. In most traditional stall inception models [9, 12, 13], a blade row is modelled as an actuator disk, which connects the upstream and the downstream flow parameters through a jump relation. In

this way, only the integral effect of the blade row could be included, while the blade geometry features and therefore the blade loading distributions can hardly be embodied. It has been reported in the open literatures that the three-dimensional design features like sweep and lean [14-16], the size of the tip clearance [17, 18], and the aspect ratio have remarkable influences on the stall margin of a compressor. Wadia et al [19] compared the tolerance of two transonic compressors, one with a radial rotor and the other one with a forward swept rotor, to inlet distortion and found that the sensitivity to inlet distortion was significantly reduced with the forward swept rotor. All these facts indicate that it is of great significance to take the detailed aerodynamic features of the blade into consideration for making an accurate prediction of the stall onset of a compressor.

Recently, upon the foundations of global linear stability analysis [20] and immersed boundary theory [21, 22], Sun et al [11] proposed a general theory of flow instabilities in turbomachinery, which can take both the non-uniform flow fields and the concrete blade geometries into consideration. Therefore, this theoretical framework is naturally applicable for the prediction of the compressor flow stability with inlet distortions. Under the general theoretical framework, two kinds of reduced-order models, namely streamline model and meridional surface model [11, 23, 24], have been developed to meet the requirements of flow stability assessment during design stage. Streamline model that aims at predicting the stability of a mean streamline in the blade-to-blade surface can be used to judge the rationality of the preliminary design scheme. The results of one-dimensional compressor mean-line calculation can be used as input for the streamline model. On the other hand, by analyzing the stability of different mean streamlines in different blade-to-blade surface through streamline model, the most unstable blade-to-blade surface can be identified, which is meaningful for the compressor designers to make some specific modifications. However, streamline model do not include the flow interaction between the blade-to-blade surfaces at different spanwise locations but analyzes the stability of each streamline separately. Thus, although streamline model is quite time-efficient, it cannot provide an accurate assessment of the flow stability of the compressor. A more complicated model, meridional surface model, which takes the throughflow in the hub-to-casing surface as input, was developed to make a quantitative assessment of the compressor flow stability. The accuracy of this model has been validated against experimental results of different kinds of compressors varying from low-speed to transonic axial and centrifugal compressors [11, 25-27]. By using this model, the effects of aerodynamic sweep on the stall behaviour of transonic compressors were analyzed [24, 28]. To the best of my knowledge, it is the first time that the adverse influences of backward sweep on the compressor flow stability were demonstrated through linear stability theory.

In this paper, both streamline model and meridional surface model are used to analyze the flow stability of a transonic compressor (NASA Rotor 37) operating with

radial inlet flow distortion. Firstly, the steady flow fields of Rotor 37 with clean inlet conditions and different radial inlet distortions are calculated by solving the Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations with $k-\varepsilon$ turbulence model. Secondly, the effects of radial inlet distortions on the overall characteristics and the blade loading at the tip region are analyzed. Then, streamline model is used to find the stability weakest part of the compressor and indicate the variation tendency of the flow stability due to the radial inlet distortion. The quantitative assessment of the effects of radial inlet distortion on the compressor flow stability is made based on meridional surface model. Lastly, the forward sweep feature is introduced to enhance the compressor tolerance to radial inlet distortions.

II. Basic Theory of Compressor Flow Instability

With some small-scale unsteadiness being ignored, which is generally caused by the blade-to-blade non-uniformity and the unsteady blade wakes, the inner flow field can be regarded as steady before the compressor falling into rotating stall state. Rotating stall is an inherent unsteady phenomenon and represents the breakdown of the steady flow field in compressors, which will inevitably occur when the mass flow through the compressor reduces to a critical value. The stability assessment of a compressor operating at a constant speed line is essentially to find the minimal mass flow rate at which the compressor can still operate normally.

Linear stability analysis is a classical and important tool to determine the critical condition under which a certain instability phenomenon occurs. For a given hydrodynamic system, its stability depends on its response to any possible small disturbance imposed on it. If any arbitrary small disturbance introduced would gradually die down, the system is deemed to be stable; if there exists a particular disturbance growing in such a way that the hydrodynamic system progressively departs from the initial state and never reverts to it, the system is unstable.

In fluid mechanics, linear stability analysis has been evolving in scope and complexity in the past decades. In the early days, limited by the computational ability, linear stability analysis was usually used to analyse very simple flow fields with no more than one inhomogeneous spatial direction, such as Poiseuille flow. For these parallel or quasi-parallel flow fields, only the flow field in a local transverse section is needed for linear stability analysis. Therefore, this type of analysis is called local stability analysis. However, the practical flow fields of interest are usually strongly non-uniform, such as the compressor flow field, for which local stability analysis is inappropriate. Therefore, it is necessary to develop a global treatment of the stability problem without sacrificing the non-uniformity of the base flow fields and the complicated geometries. The progress achieved in computational resources and algorithms for flow field simulation and large-scale eigenvalue calculation makes it possible for us

to perform global stability analysis towards much more complicated flow fields.

A. Global Linear Stability Analysis

The dynamics of the flow fields in compressors is governed by Navier-Stokes equations, which can be incompressible or compressible according to the specific application. Without loss of generality, the nonlinear governing equations are expressed in an abstract form

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{q}}{\partial t} = \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{q}), \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{q} denotes the unknown vector whose components are density, velocity and pressure, and $\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{q})$ denotes the remaining parts of the governing equations including the convective, the pressure gradient, the viscous, the heat conductive and the body-force terms.

An important step of linear stability analysis is to impose a small-amplitude disturbance on the steady base flow, then the transient flow field can be denoted by the summation of the base flow and the small-amplitude disturbance, namely

$$\mathbf{q}(r, \theta, z, t) = \bar{\mathbf{q}}(r, \theta, z) + \mathbf{q}'(r, \theta, z, t) \quad (2)$$

with $\bar{\mathbf{q}}$ and \mathbf{q}' represent the steady base flow and the unsteady small-amplitude disturbance, respectively. Here both the base flow and the disturbance are three-dimensional. Hence, the non-uniformities of the flow fields in compressors can be fully considered.

By substituting the decomposition into Eq.(1), subtracting out the zero-order terms and neglecting the higher-order infinitesimal terms, we obtain the linearized equations

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{q}'}{\partial t} = \mathbf{L}(\bar{\mathbf{q}})\mathbf{q}' \quad (3)$$

with respect to the small disturbance, where $\mathbf{L}(\bar{\mathbf{q}})$ is the linear stability operator and is a function of the base flow $\bar{\mathbf{q}}$.

As mentioned before, the stability of a hydrodynamic system depends on its response to all possible small disturbances. It is impossible to identify the evolution tendency of every small disturbance. Therefore a much more cost-efficient and smart method is called for. Considering that the linear system defined by Eq.(3) satisfies the superposition principle, this can be accomplished by expressing an arbitrary initial disturbance as a superposition of certain basic modes that separately satisfy Eq.(3) and examining the stability of the hydrodynamic system with respect to each of these modes.

For the most general base flow with three inhomogeneous spatial directions, $\mathbf{L}(\bar{\mathbf{q}})$ varies with all the three spatial coordinates. According to the method of separation of variables, Eq.(3) has solutions of this form

$$\mathbf{q}'(r, \theta, z, t) = \hat{\mathbf{q}}(r, \theta, z) \exp(-i\omega t), \quad (4)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{q}}$ represents the amplitude distribution of the three-dimensional infinitesimal disturbance.

By substituting Eq.(4) into Eq.(3), the dependence on time can be eliminated and the resulting equations

$$-i\omega \hat{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{L}(\bar{\mathbf{q}})\hat{\mathbf{q}} \quad (5)$$

will involve ω as a parameter. Eq.(5) with appropriate homogeneous boundary conditions becomes an eigenvalue problem with ω and \hat{q} as the eigenvalue and eigenfunction, respectively. In general, the eigenvalue ω is a complex number

$$\omega = \omega_r + i\omega_i, \quad (6)$$

where ω_r and ω_i denotes the oscillating frequency and the growth rate of the disturbance, respectively. According to the form of the solution in Eq.(4), if $\omega_i > 0$, the amplitude of the disturbance will increase; if $\omega_i < 0$, the disturbance will die away along with time. Hence, the sign of ω_i is an indicator for the stability of the hydrodynamic system.

B. Simplification of the Base Flow

Fully three-dimensional global stability analysis will result in a large-scale matrix, which requires extremely enormous memory and poses a big challenge for solving the eigenvalue problem. As a consequence, we have to make a compromise between the solvability and the accuracy of the model. For compressor flow stability analysis, some simplifications of the base flow need to be made according to the specific operating condition and the required precision. Generally the simplifications of the base flow refer to the reduced-order treatments of the base flow.

It is a common simplification that the compressor inner flow field is assumed to be axisymmetric. Practice has proven that the axisymmetric flow model can well reflect the work process of a compressor operating with clean or radial distortion inlet conditions although the blade-to-blade non-uniformities are ignored. With the axisymmetric assumption, the base flow for stability analysis only has two inhomogeneous directions, and $L(\bar{q})$ is just a function with respect to the radial and the axial coordinates. Since $L(\bar{q})$ is independent with the circumferential coordinate, the solution of Eq.(3) can be further expressed as

$$\mathbf{q}'(r, \theta, z, t) = \hat{\mathbf{q}}(r, z) \exp(-i\omega t + m\theta). \quad (7)$$

Then the evolution tendency of each circumferential mode can be identified one by one. The scale of the resultant eigenvalue problem will be significantly reduced. By the way, it should be emphasized that when the base flow is circumferentially non-uniform, the disturbance fields can still be expanded as Fourier series due to the natural periodic condition in circumferential direction. However, each single term of the Fourier series does not satisfy the governing equations. In other words, the circumferential modes coupled with each other due to the circumferential non-uniformities. That is why we do not expand Eq.(4) with respect to θ when the base flow is fully three-dimensional.

In the following sections, the flow stability of a transonic compressor operating with radial total pressure distortions will be analyzed with both streamline model [11] and meridional surface model [11, 24]. Both of these

two stall inception models were established under the assumption of axisymmetric flow. The readers interested in the details of these models are referred to Refs [11, 24, 28].

III. Radial Inlet Distortions

The famous NASA Rotor 37, a typical transonic isolated rotor, is adopted to investigate the effects of radial total pressure distortions on the stall behaviour. The detailed geometry design specifications and experimental results of Rotor 37 are available in Refs [29-31]. Table 1 lists the main aerodynamic design parameters.

Table 1 Design specifications of NASA Rotor 37

PARAMETER	DESIGN VALUE
Total Pressure Ratio	2.106
Total Temperature Ratio	1.270
Adiabatic Efficiency	0.877
Head Rise Coefficient	0.333
Flow Coefficient	0.453
Mass Flow, kg/s	20.188
Wheel Speed, rpm	17188.7
Tip Speed, m/s	454.14
Hub/Tip Radius Ratio	0.70
Aspect Ratio	1.19
Number of Rotor Blades	36
Blading Type	Multiple Circular Arc

Fig. 1 The Meridional Surface of NASA Rotor 37

The compressor operating with uniform inlet conditions has been analyzed in our previous paper [24]. The steady flow fields were calculated by solving the Reynolds averaged Navier-Stokes equations with $k-\epsilon$ turbulence model. For the inlet section, a uniform boundary condition including total temperature (288.15K), total pressure (101325Pa) and velocity direction (perpendicular to the inlet section) was set. The radial equilibrium condition was given for the outlet section, and the compressor throttling process was simulated by gradually increasing the outlet static pressure. As for the solid walls in the computational domain, the non-slip and adiabatic conditions were used. The comparison of the

experimental and calculated overall characteristics of Rotor 37 operating at design speed is shown in Fig. 2. We can see that the calculated total pressure ratio is slightly higher than the experimental data, while the calculated adiabatic efficiency is slightly lower than the experimental data. The small discrepancy between the calculated and experimental results is acceptable.

(a) Total Pressure Ratio

(b) Adiabatic Efficiency

Fig. 2 The Overall Characteristic of Rotor 37 Operating with Uniform Inlet Condition

It is noted that although the mass flow rate of the calculated choked point is quite close with that of the experimentally observed choked point, the ‘stability boundary’ of the steady computation is far away from the experimentally determined stability limit, which tells us that we cannot determine the stability limit of a compressor just simply through steady numerical simulation. Because the rotating stall is essentially an unsteady phenomenon, the occurrence of which must be predicted by unsteady approaches. Meridional surface model was the very appropriate tool for this problem. The calculated steady flow fields corresponding to different throttling states were entered into the model one by one. The most unstable eigenvalue for each steady flow field can be obtained. Figure 3 presents the evolution of the damping factor (the imaginary part of the eigenvalue) along with the throttling process. According to the linear stability theory, once the damping factor shifts from negative to positive, the compressor flow is deemed to become unstable. Figure 3 shows that the damping factor crosses zero when the mass flow rate is about 19.38kg/s, which is very close with the experimental data 19.40kg/s. The good agreement demonstrates that the validity of the developed model in predicting the stall inception point of a compressor.

Fig. 3 The Evolution of the Damping Factor along with the Throttling Process

After the flow stability of Rotor 37 with uniform inlet conditions being predicted by using meridional surface model, that of the same rotor operating with radial inlet distortions will be analyzed in the following sections.

A. Numerical Cases Setup

Radial inlet distortion is an idealized simplification of the real inlet distortions. The inlet distortion caused by the growth of the boundary layers may resemble the radial inlet distortion most. Other much more complicated inlet distortions, such as that caused by flow separations in the intake, can be artificially decomposed into two elementary types of distortion, namely the radial and circumferential distortions. It is noted that the radial inlet distortions of interest generally locate near the casing. In experimental investigations, the radial inlet distortions are usually generated by inserting a radial screen into the inlet duct, which covers some percent of the annulus area in the tip region. In the following, a transonic compressor (NASA Rotor 37) operating with radial inlet total pressure distortions of different intensities and ranges will be investigated. The inlet distortions are directly introduced by exerting a radially non-uniform inlet total pressure condition at the inlet section. In the outer span region, a total pressure loss is superimposed on the originally uniform total pressure (101325Pa). Four cases with different radially distorted inlet conditions are chosen. The case with uniform inlet condition and the cases with radial inlet distortions are listed in Table 2, which are labelled as Case I to Case V in turn. Figure 4 gives the visual representations of the radial total pressure distribution at the inlet section for these cases.

Table 2 Numerical Cases Setup

Cases	Total Pressure Loss (Pa)	Distortion Range (Outer Span)
Case I	0	0
Case II	2500	10%
Case III	5000	20%
Case IV	2500	10%
Case V	5000	20%

Fig. 4 The Spanwise Distributions of Total Pressure at the Inlet Section

B. Overall Performances

The steady flow fields of the compressor operating with different radially distorted inlet conditions at the design rotating speed during the throttling process are obtained through steady numerical viscous simulation whose setup except for the inlet condition is kept the same with that used in the case with uniform and standard inlet condition. Figure 5 presents the comparison of the overall characteristics of Rotor 37 operating with different inlet conditions. It can be seen that with the increase of the range or the intensity of the inlet distortion, both the total pressure ratio and the adiabatic efficiency will decline. The mass flow rate at the choked point will reduce due to the total pressure inlet distortion, while the mass flow rate at the numerical divergent point may increase or decrease for inlet distortion of different range and intensity. As we have mentioned before, the numerical divergent point cannot be simply equated with the stall inception point. Therefore, the effect of radial inlet distortion on the stability boundary needs to be predicted with unsteady approaches carefully.

(b) Adiabatic Efficiency
Fig. 5 The Overall Characteristics of Rotor 37 with Different Radial Inlet Distortions

C. Analysis of Steady Flow Fields

Before we predicting the stall inception points of Rotor 37 operating with different radial inlet distortions, the changes of the steady flow fields due to radial inlet distortions are analyzed. The radial inlet distortions mainly affect the radial profiles of axial velocity and thus the relative incident angle. Therefore, the blade loading will be redistributed radially, which is closely related to the flow stability. The spanwise distributions of axial velocity and the relative incident angle of Case I to Case V at peak efficiency point are shown in Fig. 6. The observation station is located at immediately upstream of the blade leading edge. Fig. 6 (a) shows that due to the existence of the total pressure loss superimposed on the outer span, the axial velocity in this region demonstrates an obvious reduction. According to the knowledge of velocity triangle, the relative incident angle are calculated. From Fig. 6 (b), we can see that the relative incident angle increases when a total pressure loss is introduced at the inlet section. The larger the total pressure loss is introduced, the larger the relative incident angle is.

(a) Total Pressure Ratio

(a) Axial Velocity

(b) Relative Incident Angle

Fig. 6 The Comparison of Radial Profiles of (a) Axial Velocity and (b) Relative Incident Angle at the Inlet Section of Rotor 37 with Different Inlet Conditions at Peak Efficiency Point

Figure 7 compares the distributions of the blade loading coefficient at 95% span of Rotor 37 operating with different inlet conditions at peak efficiency point. It can be seen that with the increase of the intensity of total pressure distortion, the blade loading at the tip region will significantly increase, especially for the front part of the blade tip. Higher blade loading at the tip region usually means much worse and more complicated tip leakage flow, which may badly deteriorate the compressor flow stability.

Fig. 7 The Comparison of Blade Loading Coefficient at Tip Region of Rotor 37 with Different Inlet Conditions at Peak Efficiency Point

IV. Results of Linear Stability Analysis

For compressors operating with radial inlet distortions, the length scale of the circumferential non-uniformity of the base flow is on the order of the pitch, which is relatively small in comparison with the circumference, thus the circumferential non-uniformity can be ignored in analyzing the flow stability. In this section, both streamline model and meridional surface model will be used to predict the effects of radial inlet distortions on the compressor flow stability. As we have reviewed in the introduction section, streamline model can make a quick prediction of the flow stability of a mean streamline in the blade-to-blade surface, which can be used to indicate the weakest part of the compressor in flow stability aspect, while meridional surface model takes the throughflow in the hub-to-casing surface as input and can make an accurate prediction of the compressor stability boundary.

A. Streamline Model

The stability of the blade-to-blade flow field at a specific span is predicted by using streamline model. Whether the flow is stable or not is indicated by the sign of damping factor (the imaginary part of the eigenvalue). Blade-to-blade flow fields at three span locations, 100%, 95% and 90% span, are analyzed. Figure 8(a) and Fig. 8(b) present the predicting results of Rotor 37 operating with clean inlet condition (Case I) and radial inlet distortion (Case III), respectively. These two figures show that for both Case I and Case III, all the damping factors of the selected three blade-to-blade surfaces increase monotonically with the decrease of the mass flow rate, which means the flow field becomes more and more unstable during the throttling process. Comparing the damping factors of the blade-to-blade flow field at three different span locations, we can see that the stability of the blade-to-blade flow at the outer span is worse than that of the inner span, which is of notable regularity for all these five cases. In other words, no matter whether the inlet condition is clean or distorted, the stability of the flow in the blade-to-blade surface near the casing is the weakest part in the compressor.

(a) With Clean Inlet Condition (Case I)

(b) With Radial Inlet Distortion (Case III)

Fig. 8 The Comparison of Flow Stability of Streamlines at Different Spanwise Positions

Figure 9(a) compares the stability of the blade-to-blade surface flow at the same spanwise position (100%) of Case I, Case II and Case III. A remarkable tendency can be seen that the stronger the radial inlet distortion is, the stability of the blade-to-blade surface flow is worse. Figure 9(b) compares the stability of the blade-to-blade surface flow at 100% spanwise location of Case I, Case IV and Case V. It also indicates that with a total pressure loss superimposed on the inlet section, the stability of the blade-to-blade surface flow is deteriorated. Here we just present the results of 100% spanwise location. In fact, other blade-to-blade surfaces (95% and 90% spanwise location) have the same regularity.

(a) With Total Pressure Distortion in the Outer 20% Span (Case II & Case III)

(b) With Total Pressure Distortion in the Outer 10% Span (Case IV & Case V)

Fig. 9 The Comparison of Flow Stability of Streamlines at 100% Spanwise Position of Rotor 37 Operating with Different Inlet Conditions

Since streamline model just takes the flow field in a single blade-to-blade surface as input, the spanwise non-uniformity and the interaction between the blade-to-blade surfaces at different spanwise locations cannot be included, the prediction results are not accurate from the aspect of the predicted stall inception points. Even so, streamline model can still indicate the flow stability difference between different spanwise locations. In addition, the deteriorating effects of the radial inlet distortions on the flow stability can also be captured qualitatively. A more accurate prediction can be made by using meridional model.

B. Meridional Surface Model

By using meridional surface model, the effects of radial inlet distortion on the flow stability of Rotor 37 will be assessed. The accuracy of meridional surface model has been validated against a variety of compressors. Moreover, the prediction result of Rotor 37 operating with clean inlet condition agrees the experimental result very well. Therefore, we deem that meridional surface model is an accurate and reliable tool to predict the flow stability of compressors operating with radial inlet distortions.

Figure 10(a) shows the flow stability of Rotor 37 operating with clean inlet condition (Case I) and with a total pressure loss in the outer 20% span (Case II and Case III). For all the three cases, with the decrease of the mass flow rate, the compressor flow tends to be more and more unstable. The point at which the sign of the damping factor shifts is the theoretically predicted stall inception point. The predicted mass flow rates at stall inception point for Case I, Case II and Case III are about 19.38kg/s, 19.46kg/s and 19.60kg/s, respectively. Figure 10(b) presents the flow stability of Rotor 37 operating with clean inlet condition (Case I) and with a total pressure loss in the outer 10% span (Case IV and Case V). The predicted mass flow rates at stall inception point for Case I, Case IV and Case V are 19.38kg/s, 19.48kg/s and 19.53kg/s, respectively. These results indicate that the radial inlet distortion can indeed narrow the stable operation range of a compressor. With the increase of the intensity and covering range of the radial inlet distortion, the stable operation range of a compressor would reduce monotonically.

(a) With Total Pressure Distortion in the Outer 20% Span (Case II & Case III)

(b) With Total Pressure Distortion in the Outer 10% Span (Case IV & Case V)

Fig. 10 The Comparison of Flow Stability of Rotor 37 Operating with Different Inlet Conditions

V. Enhance the Tolerance to Radial Distortion with Forward Sweep

By using streamline model, it is revealed that the outer span is the most unstable part in this compressor, which can be seen from Fig. 8. Figure 7 shows that the blade loading in the outer span increases due to the radial inlet distortion superimposed. Higher blade loading at the tip region has adverse effects on the compressor flow stability, which has been verified through the calculations based on streamline model and meridional surface model. A natural thought is that if the increase of the blade loading can be controlled, the loss of the stable operation range caused by the radial inlet distortion is possible to be reduced.

It has been reported that forward sweep is beneficial to improve the flow field and alleviate the blade loading at the tip region. In this section, the potential of forward sweep in lowering the unfavorable influence of radial inlet distortions on the flow stability is investigated. The forward sweep feature is introduced by moving the blade element at 100% spanwise location along the chordwise direction for 10% of the chord length, the blade elements between 0 and 90% spanwise location are kept fixed.

Figure 11 compares the flow stability of streamline at 99% span location between radial rotor and forward swept rotor operating with a total pressure loss of 5000Pa covering the outer 10% span. It can be seen that with the decrease of the mass flow rate, the damping factor of the radial rotor grows faster than that of the forward swept rotor, which indicates that the forward sweep feature used can improve the stability of the flow field at the tip region.

Fig. 11 The Comparison of Flow Stability of Streamline at 99% Span Location Between Radial Rotor and Forward Swept Rotor Operating with a Total Pressure Loss of 5000Pa Covering the Outer 10% Span

The quantitative assessment of the improvement of the compressor flow stability due to forward sweep feature is made based on meridional surface model. Figure 12 compares the flow stability between radial rotor and forward swept rotor operating with a total pressure loss of 5000Pa covering the outer 10% span. The damping factors of radial rotor and forward swept rotor shift from negative to positive at 19.53kg/s and 19.36kg/s, respectively, which confirms that the forward sweep feature indeed offsets the harmful effect of the radial inlet distortion on the flow stability.

Fig. 12 The Comparison of Flow Stability Between Radial Rotor and Forward Swept Rotor Operating with a Total Pressure Loss of 5000Pa Covering the Outer 10% Span

VI. Conclusions

The effects of radial inlet distortion on the compressor flow stability were investigated based on global linear stability analysis. The steady flow fields of a transonic compressor (NASA Rotor 37) operating with clean inlet condition and radial inlet distortions were calculated. The analyses of the steady flow fields showed that the total pressure loss introduced in the inlet section induces the increase of the angle of attack and thus higher blade loading at the tip region.

Streamline model can be used to indicate the weakest part of flow stability in compressors, while meridional model is capable of making an accurate prediction of the stability boundary. Streamline model revealed that the tip

region is the most unstable part in the compressor, and with the increase of the intensity of the radial inlet distortion, the stability of the flow field in the tip region gradually worsens. Meridional surface model further confirmed the unfavorable influence of radial inlet distortion on the flow stability and gave a quantitative assessment of the stall margin loss due to radial inlet distortion.

The stability analysis results showed that the compressor flow stability has a strong correlation with the blade loading level of the tip region. The forward sweep feature was adopted to offset the harmful effects of the increase of the blade loading at the tip region induced by the radial inlet distortion, the validity of which was confirmed by streamline model and meridional model.

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